

NOMINATIVE SENTENCE AND SEMANTIC GRADATION

Makhmudov Muzaffar Mamirovich

**Seniour Lecturer of the Department of Foreign Language and Literature,
Taskent University of Applied Sciences**

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Annotation: The question of the theory of graduality and the degree of its spread in nominative sentences is considered, the semantic connections of evaluative-existential nominative sentences and the text are determined. The author defines the degree of manifestation of graduation signs in nominative sentences as an additional (partial) one, since such syntactic models are characterized by the presence of transitional phenomena.

Key words: nominative sentence, text, gradual semantics, speech evaluation.

The complexity of the language structure and the dynamics of its functioning in the Russian language have recently been leading in determining the foundations of modern linguistics. Along with the development of the doctrine of supply, it becomes necessary to determine not only its external indicators, but also to identify the difference between the demand and the real reality. In the modern language system, there is a tendency to formalize speech with the obligatory reflection of a feature that is the result of the speaker's gradation relations to the objects, things, and events surrounding him. This approach generates specific features of grading semantics.

According to S. M. Kolesnikova, graduality is a functional and semantic category expressing a measuring approach to reality in terms of "more (than) / less (than)" in various ways (due to pronominal words, particles, words of subjective assessment, adverbs of measure and degree, etc.) [2, p. 48]. The essence of grading is the gradual increase or decrease of the graded quantities contained in the graded predicate.

The semantics of grading is based on the nature of its semantic components. Each of the external components of the gradation forms the property to express the determined values to a greater or lesser extent. The characteristic of the degree of their signs is related to the mental activity of the subject expressing his attitude to the real picture of the world.

Our interest in the semantics of grading prompted us to turn to one of the types of nominative applications capable of expressing a subjective assessment — nominative evaluative quantitative-evaluative sentences.

The main feature of a nominative sentence is the assertion of the existence of objects or phenomena expressed in the form of the nominative case or a quantitative noun phrase: *Evening. Half past five (A. Vasilevskaya. A book about life)*. Undifferentiated nominative sentences, being widely represented in speech, can perform various functions: serve to characterize a person: *The Englishman. Twenty years old (S. Solovyov. Adam's Bridge)*; to show the presence of an object in a subject-spatial environment: *The key. Number 080 (Yu. Buida. Konigsberg)*, etc. V. V. Babaytseva, sentences of this type are classified as evaluative-existential, which contain an emotional qualitative or quantitative characteristic of the predicate (semantics of characterization) [1, p. 25].

The structure of the semantics of graduality includes three main components: the grading subject, the graded object, the nature and the basis of grading. The graduated subject is characterized by the expression of subjective modality, the nature of graduation is determined by the semantics of the increase or decrease of the attribute. In a graded context,

semantic interpretation primarily depends on the speech situation, the purpose of communication and the text, which is the defining component of semantic grading.: *The family had been scattered all over the world, and now they were coming together to enjoy meeting real Russian relatives, but with the help of that old culture from which everyone had already been excommunicated.*

The main sentence from the nominative series is *What an English speech!* — projects the rest of the sentences, consistently reflecting the real picture of the world. These nominative sentences were graded in the form of simple sentences with a common word *what*. The purity and quality of the emigrants' speech act as the basis in the graded-evaluative statement. The subjects of graduation are determined by the context — a family consisting of emigrants. The semantic role of sentence members (predicates) is determined by the communicative significance of the information that the entire sentence contains — admiration for the quality of speech and manners of these people. As part of exclamation nominative sentences, the pronominal word **which** performs a dual role, depending on the structure of the sentence. On the one hand, it replaces qualitative adjectives that are missing in the context.

In a nominative sentence with graded semantics, the meaning of the utterance depends primarily on the speech situation, the purpose of communication and the context. The role of context is not limited to clarifying and specifying what is expressed by the grammatical form of the predicate. Due to the context, the general semantic function is determined in the nominative sentence [3].

The complex nature of the category of graduality is due to the specifics of linguistic means and pragmatic meaning. So, in the sentence *"What kind of look is there! Fields, fields, hills, a church on an Island, villages... Women on the lake are rinsing their laundry, the water reflects their voices"* (A. Vasilevsky. *A book about life*) it is possible to distinguish graduation according to different axes — nature, lake, church, women engaged in household chores. A common fragment of the captured picture acts as a grouping feature in this context. Graduation is mostly implicit here, including the use of graphic means (exclamation, ellipsis). The author includes nominative series in the text to achieve a communicative goal in speech [4].

Thus, the graded semantics is formed by words with changeable and unchangeable features, as well as by introducing into the structure the components most significant for the semantic interpretation of the utterance (intonation, particles, determinative pronouns, etc.).

The study of the semantics of graduality in the nominative sense is not new in science, however, it is necessary to identify various semantic shades when interpreting a text as a super—phrasal unity. The semantic shades presented in the nominative sentence make it possible to diversify the grammatical structure of the language, determining one or another degree of the expressed feature and thereby determining its place in the linguistic picture of the world.

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